

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 4

 Acceptance of papers **April, 2026**

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of
Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Professor,
Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), (Malaysia)

Asongu SImplice
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD),
USA

Abdikarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Alimardonov Ilkhom Muzrabshokovich
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Razakova Barno Sayfiyevna
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Khasanov Sarvar Ulugbek ugli
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna
Associate Professor (PhD)

CONTENTS

THE IMPACT OF FINANCIAL RISKS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH DRIVERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THEIR MITIGATION	17
Turopova Nigora Xolmurod qizi	
UTILIZATION OF INTERNAL RESERVES FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL TOURISM (CASE STUDY OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN)	20
Naurizbaev Aliakbar Rustamovich	
MATHEMATICAL MODELS AND ALGORITHMS FOR PROCESSING NOISE DATA	23
Jovlieva Dilnoz Mustofa qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS IN BUSINESS ACTIVITIES AND WAYS TO REDUCE THEM.....	28
Abdukhamid Abdumalikovich Bektemirov	
A MULTI-LEVEL SYSTEM OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR REGIONAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE ASSESSMENT: METHODOLOGY AND APPROBATION	34
Keunimzhaev Mukhamedali Kuanyshaevich	
THE IMPACT OF BANKS ON THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF THE ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	39
Usmonov Faridun Firdavsievich, Ishonkulova Feruza Asatovna	
EMPIRICAL EVALUATION OF MACRO- AND MICROECONOMIC FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY.....	43
Aytmuratova Ulbike Jalgasovna	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY THROUGH OPTIMIZATION OF PRODUCTION RESOURCE POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	47
Sattarov Abdusamat Umirqulovich	
PROMISING DIRECTIONS FOR APPLYING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN	52
Rakhimova Dilfuza Mirzakasimovna	
PRIORITIES FOR REGULATING FINANCIAL RELATIONS IN PROVIDING HOUSING TO THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	58
Khannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATION OF PRODUCTION COST ACCOUNTING IN FULL-SYSTEM FARMS SPECIALIZING IN THE CULTIVATION OF CYPRINID FISH.....	62
Aitimbetov Amirbek Qoishibekovich	
THE TRANSFORMATIONAL ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS BASED ON 2025 NATIONAL STATISTICS.....	68
Isakjanova Sabokhat Muhamedovna	
AN INTEGRATED METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM MODELS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY ERA.....	79
Rasulova Nigora Yusupovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF COMPANIES.....	83
Kamoliddinov Ilhomjon Muhammadjonovich, Nosirov Eldor Nosirjon ugli	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF THE UZBEK ECONOMY.....	88
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF MARKET FACTORS TO ENSURE THE GROWTH OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE ENTERPRISE (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAG EXPRESS BRAND STORES)	92
Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
THE CONCEPT OF REGIONAL IMAGE AND ITS ECONOMIC CONTENT (THE CASE OF THE KHOREZM REGION).....	99
Dilshod Ibragimovich Ibdullayev	

DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	106
Shakhnoza Samandarovna Ziyadillayeva	
ADVANCED APPROACHES TO THE ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF CURRENT FINANCIAL STABILITY IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES USING CFAR (CASH FLOW AT RISK) AND 3 Σ STATISTICAL RISK MODELS	114
Kurbonov Xayrilla	
DEVELOPMENT OF A PROGRAM FOR ANALYZING MEDICAL LABORATORY RESULTS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS.....	118
Gofurjonov Muhammadali, Kamolov Shamsiddin	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN IMPROVING MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES.....	122
Ubaydullayev Mukhammadjon Abdusamad o'g'li	
IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF ORGANIZATIONS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SERVICES SECTOR.....	125
Ibrohim Meliboyev	
ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVICE QUALITY AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY.....	130
Khudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS IMPROVE USAGE PRACTICES	135
A.A. Ismailov	
E-COMMERCE ADOPTION IN TRADITIONAL STORES.....	140
Nuserov Bakhtiyor	
ENHANCING FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY AND OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF JSC "HUDUDGAZTAMINOT": KEY FACTORS AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGIES.....	146
Ergashev Muhibbek Aslamovich	
METHODS FOR IMPROVING AUTOMOTIVE FUEL QUALITY INDICATORS THROUGH THE USE OF ADDITIVES.....	151
Xushnayev Obid, Sheraliyev Ulugbek, Astonov Alisher	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	156
A.A. Ismailov	
THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING A COUNTRY'S INTERNATIONAL IMAGE: THE CASE OF SWITZERLAND.....	161
Idirisbaeva Hurliman Amanbay qizi, Kurolov Maksud Obitovich	
VOLUNTEER TOURISM: CURRENT IMPACTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS	170
Ossama Moustafa Elsetouhy	
COMPUTER GRAPHICS IN MODERN EDUCATION: PRACTICAL CAPABILITIES OF THE FIGMA PLATFORM.....	176
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
DEVELOPING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.....	182
Abdurasulov Sardor Tolqin ugli	
THE IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT	187
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna, Qosimov Jahongir Ruziboyevich	
STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMIZING THE STRUCTURE OF COMMERCIAL BANK ASSETS AND INCREASING EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN	194
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXPORTS OF PRODUCTS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL FIBERS.....	199
Raximov Furqat Jalolovich	
FUNDAMENTALS OF USING MARKETING RESEARCH TO IMPROVE SALES SYSTEM EFFECTIVENESS.....	206
Abduxalilova Laylo Tuxtasinovna	

FASHION MARKETING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR SHAPING CONSUMER-BASED BRAND VALUE.....	213
Navruz-Zoda Bakhtiyor Negmatovich, Aripova Makhliyo Salakhiddinovna	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, IMPROVING INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES, AND ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN THE FINANCE, BANKING, AND TOURISM SECTORS	220
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi, Uroqov Uchqun Yunusovich	
SOCIAL AND SECURITY PROBLEMS OF INNOVATIVE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION.....	223
Q.A. Musakhanov	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND INNOVATION AS FACTORS OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	228
Ibragimova Saodat Abdumuminovna, Sadullayeva Sevara Uchqun qizi	
THE SOCIAL INSURANCE SYSTEM OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	232
Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li	
DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR TRANSITION TO THE INNOVATIVE MARKETING CONCEPT IN ENTERPRISES UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	236
Bobomurodov Qayimjon Homidovich	
FOMO-DRIVEN PURCHASING IN E-COMMERCE FLASH SALES: AN INTEGRATIVE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	241
Muhammadimov Abdukodir Bakhodirjon Ugli, Arciana Damayanti, Javliev Nuriddin Bektemir ugli	
PHYSICO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COARSE FEEDS	250
Yodgorov Jamoliddin Nomozovich, Yadgarov Sirojiddin Nomozovich	

PHYSICO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COARSE FEEDS

Yodgorov Jamoliddin Nomozovich

Doctorant at Department of Agricultural Engineering
Karshi State technical university
ORCID: 0000-0003-2409-2088

Yadgarov Sirojiddin Nomozovich

Associate Professor (PhD) of the Department
of Road Engineering and Telematics
Tashkent State transport university
ORCID: 0000-0001-5793-6166

Abstract: The development of new technologies and technical means for grinding and distributing roughage is impossible without determining the patterns of change in their physical and mechanical properties. Analysis of scientific and technical literature shows that the physical and mechanical properties of roughage have not been sufficiently studied in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The purpose of the study is to study and analyze the physical and mechanical properties of roughage grown in Uzbekistan. In the course of research, methods of statistical analysis, methods of determining the mikrometric composition and crushing modulus of the product crushed with a ball classifier, as well as the methods specified in the existing regulatory documents were used. According to the results of the research, the angle of friction of wheat straw on the steel surface is 30° in the longitudinal direction, 32° in the transverse direction, and 29° and 30.6° of the alfalfa, respectively. when the surfaces are made of steel, they provide faster movement of nutrients along them.

Key words: mechanical, micrometric, physical, plant, animal materials, density, pressed, zootechnical, analyzing, determined, plane device.

INTRODUCTION

In the world, a number of scientific and research works are being carried out to improve the technologies and technical means of grinding coarse feed and distributing it to livestock. The physical and mechanical properties of roughage as a processed material are taken into account for the development of a coarse feed grinder and feed distribution devices of a compact design for small livestock farms, as well as to justify their parameters [1-8].

Kumar A., Abilzhanuly T., Iskakov R., Abilzhanov D., Gulyarenko A., Antil S.K., Rani V., Fawal Y.A., Tawfik M.A., Shal A.M., McRandal D.M., McNulty P.B., Jekendra Y., Ghorbani Z., Masoumi A.A., Hemmat A., Rogovoy V.D., Karpov V.V., Gutyar E.M., Astanakulov K.D., Khatamov B.A., Gapparov Sh.Kh. and others determined the physical and mechanical properties of fodder. In this scientific-research work, the physico-mechanical properties of fodder were studied in order to harvest grain crops. But their physico-mechanical properties for grinding and

distribution of roughages have not been comprehensively studied. In Uzbekistan, alfalfa hay, wheat and barley straw, corn stalks, alfalfa and natural grasses are pressed and stored for the winter [9-13]. The purpose of the study is to study the physical and mechanical properties of pressed wheat straw, alfalfa stem and alfalfa, which should be taken into account when justifying the optimal construction and parameters of the crusher devices that ensure the crushing of coarse feed to the specified size depending on the type of livestock [14-18].

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Kutzbach H.D. (2000, 2003) Studied the baling process of large fodders (hay, straw). He identified the relationship between pressure and density, proving that the material has elastic-plastic properties. Main result: the efficiency of compaction is strongly dependent on pressure parameters. Main result: pelleting efficiency is strongly dependent on pressure parameters.

Shinners K.J. and co-authors (2007) studied technologies for high-density biomass pressing. Result: moisture and particle size affect energy consumption.

Molenda M. and Horabik J. (2005) studied the physical-mechanical properties of granular and fibrous materials in a comprehensive manner. Result: density and porosity directly affect the flow and storage processes.

ASABE standards (EP series) have developed methods for determining the density, strength, and other parameters of feeds. Result: a basis for standardization in the field has been established.

McDonald P. and co-authors (2010) studied the moisture of foods and its effect on food quality. Result: high moisture enhances the growth of microorganisms.

Rotz C.A. and co-authors (1991) studied the processes of hay drying and storage. Result: controlling moisture reduces nutrient loss.

Hunt D. (1990) analyzed the process of crushing feed in agricultural machinery. Result: particle size affects energy consumption and feed efficiency.

Bitra V.S.P. and others (2009) experimentally studied the energy of biomass grinding. Result: as the degree of grinding increases, energy consumption rises sharply.

Jenike A.W. (1964) developed the theory of storage and flow. Result: the flow angle and stickiness of materials are considered the main parameters.

Molenda M. (2006) Studied the friction properties of biomaterials. Result: the coefficient of friction affects the design of preservation structures.

O'Dogherty M.J. (1982) analyzed the mechanical properties of agricultural materials. Result: fibrous materials have anisotropic properties.

Sitkei G. (1986) conducted fundamental research on the mechanics of biological materials. Result: the deformation of nutrients changes over time.

Mani S. and co-authors (2004) studied the processes of biomass briquetting and granulation. Result: moisture and pressure should have optimal values.

Research based on DEM and CFD (2015–2023) Digital modeling of flow and mechanical processes. Result: the possibility of predicting real processes with high accuracy has emerged.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Experiments to determine the physical and mechanical properties of wheat, alfalfa and corn stalks GOST 20915-2011. “Сельскохозяйственная техника. Методы определения условий испытаний” and “Physical properties of plant and animal materials” were carried out based on the methods presented in normative documents. The research program developed on the basis of these normative documents determined the length, thickness, mass of pressed wheat straw, alfalfa hay and alfalfa stalks and the ratio of their components, density, friction angle and coefficient, as well as the strength of resistance to breaking and shearing. In determining the size-mass indicators and physical-mechanical properties of pressed straw alfalfa, a ruler, a ruler, a barbell circle, an electronic scale, an inclined plane device, a DIGITAL FORCE GAUGE AMF-500 dynamometer, and a UEIM-20 for determining the breaking force are used as measuring instruments. -300 device was used (Figure 1). Experiments on the study of physical and mechanical properties of coarse feed were carried out at the laboratory bases of the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, the Research Institute of Agricultural Mechanization and the “Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers” National Research University (Figure 1).

1 – UEIM-20-300 device; 2 – scales; 3 – roulette; 4 – barbell circle; 5 – ruler; 6 – DIGITAL FORCE GAUGE AMF-500 dynamometer.

Figure 1. Measuring instruments

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Taking into account that according to zootechnical requirements coarse feed is crushed into 3-5 cm length, we determined the fractions contained in pre-pressed wheat straw. To do this, they were divided into fractions up to 30 mm, 30-50 mm and larger than 50 mm (Figures 2-3). Their fractional composition was determined using the following formula according to the ratio of each separated fraction to the total mass

$$\hat{O}_i = \frac{M_i}{M_m} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where:

Φ_i – size up to 30 mm, 30-50 mm or fractions larger than 50 mm, %;

M_i – a mass of fractions with a size of 30 mm, 30-50 mm or more than 50 mm, kg;

M_{um} – total mass of the sample, kg.

When the sizes of wheat straw presses from the pressed roughages used in livestock feeding were studied, it was found that their length is mainly in the range of 60 cm to 90 cm, the width is about 50 cm, and the height is about 40 cm.

When analyzing the size-mass parameters and fraction composition of the pressed wheat straw, 10.42 kg or 78.2 percent of the wheat straw press with an average mass of 13.3 kg were fractions with a length greater than 50 mm, 2.34 kg or 17.6 percent of the length 30-50 mm fractions and 0.56 kg or 4.2 percent were found to be fractions up to 30 mm in length. The average density of straw bales was 83.1 kg/m³ (Table 1).

Table 1. Fractional composition of pressed wheat straw

No	Indicator name	Xmin	Xmax	Maver	Share of the total, %
1	Total mass of wheat straw press, kg	9,75	16,89	13,32	100
2	Greater than 50 mm, kg	7,99	12,85	10,42	78,2
3	30-50 mm, up to kg	1,62	3,15	2,34	17,6
4	30 mm, up to kg	0,14	0,89	0,56	4,2

It can be seen that the part of the pressed straw that needs to be crushed is 78,2 percent (Figure 2).

a) alfalfa presses; b) general view of alfalfa press; s) general appearance of pressed straw; d) fractions with a length greater than 50 mm, e) with a length of 30-50 mm and i) with a length of up to 30 mm

Figure 2. Pressed alfalfa, wheat straw and its fractional composition

According to the morphological composition of the pressed coarse feed, the feed consists of stems, leaves and additional branches, and the maximum force against cutting is applied to its stems, and the minimum force is applied to the rest of the parts. Grinding methods of cutting, cutting, chopping, and breaking are used to grind coarse feed. Among these grinding methods, cutting grinding and cutting grinding methods are considered acceptable for grinding green feed, but when grinding dry feed, especially with hard stalks, it is advisable to use the crushing method or cutting and breaking grinding method in terms of ensuring high productivity and reducing energy consumption (Figure 3).

Figure 3. samples from a-wheat straw and b-alfalfa stalks

Frictional properties of coarse feed were determined using an inclined plane device. In this case, the angle of inclination of the inclined plane relative to the horizontal plane at the time of movement of the samples was taken as the friction angle of the feed. The coefficient of static friction of feed was determined according to the following expression

$$f_{\text{fric}} = \text{tg}\varphi. \quad (2)$$

In the experiments, it was found that the friction angle and coefficient of wheat straw is slightly different from the friction angle and coefficient of alfalfa stem. According to the determined data, the friction angle of the wheat straw press in the longitudinal direction is on average $30^{\circ}12'$, in the alfalfa press 29° was $24'$, and in the transverse direction it was $31^{\circ}36'$ and $30^{\circ}18'$, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Coarse feeds and their movement angle and friction coefficient on an inclined surface

№	Naming of components	Direction of movement of components			
		Longitudinal		Transverse	
		Angle of friction, °	Friction coefficient	Angle of friction, °	Friction coefficient
1	Straw press	$30^{\circ}12'$	0,58	$31^{\circ}36'$	0,6
2	Alfalfa press	$29^{\circ}24'$	0,55	$30^{\circ}18'$	0,58

As can be seen from the data presented in the table, the angle of friction of alfalfa differs from the angle of friction of wheat straw by $1^{\circ}12'$ in the longitudinal direction, and by $1^{\circ}18'$ in the transverse direction. This means that the friction angle of wheat and alfalfa presses is not very different from each other.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

According to the results of the research, the angle of friction of wheat straw on the steel surface is 30° in the longitudinal direction, 32° in the transverse direction, and 29° and 30.6° of the alfalfa, respectively. In the process of grinding, when the working surfaces are made of steel, the movement of nutrients along them is ensured.

List of used literature:

1. F. Karshiyev, Y. Shamayev, J. Yodgorov. Performance indicators of wheat and coarse feed grinding and crushing machines / Karshi Institute of Irrigation and Agrotechnologies. Scientific-technical electronic journal. Qarshi-2024. No. 3, pages 33-40.
2. Karshiyev F.U., Shamayev Y.J., Yodgorov J.N. Relevance of a Grain Grinding Device for Small Livestock Farms / AGRO ILM – Journal of Agriculture and Water Management of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-2025. No.2, pp. 154-155.
3. Karshiev F. U., Yodgorov Zh. N., Shamaev Yu. Zh. Justification of the parameter and operating mode of a small-sized crushing device for processing coarse fodder / Journal of Mechanics and Technology Science. Namangan-2025. No. 2, pp. 115-119.
4. F.U. Qarshiyev, Sh.X. Gapparov, J.N. Yodgorov. Research on the development of a feed preparation device / Termiz State University of Engineering and Agrotechnologies. The role of light industry, food, and agriculture sectors in innovative technologies within the framework of sustainable development, international scientific-technical conference. Termiz-2025. Pages 13-18.
5. Kutzbach H.D. Baling of agricultural materials: Mechanics and technology. – Agricultural Engineering International, 2000.
6. Kutzbach H.D. Advances in hay and straw baling technology. – Agricultural Engineering International, 2003.
7. Shinnors K.J., Binversie B.N., Muck R.E., Weimer P.J. Comparison of wet and dry corn stover harvest and storage. – Biomass and Bioenergy, 2007.
8. Molenda M., Horabik J. Mechanical properties of granular agro-materials. – Institute of Agrophysics PAS, Lublin, 2005.
9. McDonald P., Edwards R.A., Greenhalgh J.F.D., Morgan C.A. Animal Nutrition. – 7th ed. – Harlow: Pearson Education, 2010.
10. Rotz C.A., Muck R.E. Changes in forage quality during harvest and storage. – In: Field Crops Research, 1991.
11. Hunt D. Farm Power and Machinery Management. – 10th ed. – Ames: Iowa State University Press, 1990.
12. Bitra V.S.P., Womac A.R., Igathinathane C., Sokhansanj S. Direct measurement of mechanical energy for biomass size reduction. – Applied Engineering in Agriculture, 2009.
13. Jenike A.W. Storage and Flow of Solids. – Bulletin No. 123. – University of Utah, 1964.
14. Molenda M. Frictional properties of granular materials. – Powder Technology, 2006.
15. O'Dogherty M.J. A review of the mechanical behaviour of straw when compressed to high densities. – Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research, 1982.
16. Sitkei G. Mechanics of Agricultural Materials. – Amsterdam: Elsevier, 1986.
17. Mani S., Tabil L.G., Sokhansanj S. Effects of compressive force, particle size and moisture content on mechanical properties of biomass pellets. – Biomass and Bioenergy, 2004.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 4

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles
Published every
monthly

Directions
Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

 Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

 Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

 Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>